

ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY STANDARD OF FISH POND IN THE PERI-URBAN AREA, IBADAN, NIGERIA

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Abstract: Peri-urban areas are dynamic interfaces between urban and rural environments, often absorbing excessive population growth and supporting diverse livelihoods. While fish farming in these regions significantly contributes to socioeconomic growth and food security, its proliferation has introduced notable environmental challenges. This study assessed the water quality of fish ponds in the peri-urban area, Ibadan, using the Arulogun area under the Akinyele Local Government Area as a case study. A cross-sectional and experimental survey research design was used for the study, while both primary and secondary data were sourced. A purposive sampling technique was used to select fish ponds based on relevant characteristics. Each participant adequately represented different zones of Arulogun. A total of 62 fish ponds were identified, representing a 100% sample size for adequate inference. Water samples were collected from the chosen fishponds in Arulogun, Ibadan and the water quality was assessed using six metals (i.e., Lead (Pb), Copper (Cu), Chromium (Cr), Zinc (Zn), Iron (Fe), and Cadmium (Cd)). The chosen water samples were then subjected to a laboratory test. Samples were collected in polypropylene bottles that were appropriately acidified to avoid biological, chemical, and physical alterations. After being placed inside an ice box, these bottles were brought to the laboratory. Every sample was kept in a refrigerator at a temperature lower than 4 °C. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to analyse the data at a $p \leq 0.05$ confidence level. The results were compared against the World Health Organisation (WHO) standard limits for fishponds and fisheries to determine potential contamination risks. The findings indicated that there is a high level of Iron (Fe), which exceeds the WHO threshold, and it was recommended that adequate attention should be given to the peri-urban landuse development.

1.0 Introduction/ Statement of problems

Peri-urban areas are the interface of urban and rural spaces; they are dynamic regions that

absorb the excessive population of the urban areas (Tiwari, 2019; Dutta, 2020). Peri-urban areas around the world are distinguished by a

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variety of livelihoods, uneven service access, and intricate patterns of poverty and inequality. Peri-urban areas have become important locations for comprehending the relationship between urban development, rural dynamics, and socioeconomic inequities as urbanization continues to grow (Salem, 2024).

The peri-urban environment has similar components to those of the urban area. The environment cuts across every activity of man. The major components are the atmosphere (air), lithosphere (land), biosphere (Vegetation) and the hydrosphere (Water). The hydrosphere is interconnected with other spheres in the system of the earth. The hydrosphere comprises the oceans, rivers, groundwater, frozen glaciers, ice caps, and vapor (atmosphere) all covering over 70% of the surface of the earth. According to science, water is the most prevalent material on Earth's surface. Surface and ground water make up about 1.4 billion cubic kilometers (326 million cubic miles) of liquid and frozen water, but it is vulnerable to pollution and other effects of climate change due to human activity. If and when human activities in the built environment are not regulated, the water quality will be affected. Deterioration of water quality affects the physical, emotional, and environmental health of countless numbers of people globally. Approximately 3.4 million people worldwide die each year from water-related illnesses, such as cholera, typhoid, ascariasis, cryptosporidiosis, and diarrhoea; however, another study claimed that the sanitation system was partly to blame (Adejumo et al., 2025). According to the Bangladesh Demographic and Health Survey (BDHS), 5.1% of children died. Additionally,

Halder et al. (2024) found that diarrhoea was linked to 6.9% of deaths in children under the age of five. According to WHO (2015), diarrhoea was a contributing factor in approximately 01, 15, and 6% of neonatal and post-neonatal deaths. As the anthropogenic activities change land use and land cover, water quality and quantity change, thus, need to control human activities (Roşca *et al*, 2020). Some of the human activities that affect water quality are paddy cropping, livestock grazing, vegetable gardening and fish farming. Because it meets the need for animal protein, creates jobs, lowers poverty for huge populations, and generates foreign exchange, fishing operations have significantly boosted the economy and are crucial to socioeconomic growth (Yasmin et al., 2025). The fish industry helps by boosting socioeconomic development, reducing poverty, and enhancing the standard of living for underprivileged groups. Over 1.3 million people are directly employed in the fishing industry, while it is generally estimated that 12 million people in the nation are supported by fishing and related activities (FAO, 2010). Around 0.26 million hectares of land are used for freshwater fish farming, and about 2.0 million metric tons of fish are produced annually.

Fish demand in the country is 3.6 million metric tonnes, but total domestic production from all sources is only 1 080,855 metric tonnes annually, leaving a demand-supply gap of approximately 2.52 million metric tonnes in 2021 (Subasinghe et al., 2021). From the statistics, the expansion of fish farming is inevitable so is the environmental challenges in

the host neighbourhoods. Unfortunately, the urban area is fully developed and the next available region is the peri-urban area whereby there is land to excavate for fish ponds while many of this construction are done without taken cognizant of physical and the chemical properties of the soil, underground water and the waste that would be generated from the fishing activities. The impetus for this is type of study is the fish intake which would later be consumed by human being which will be risky for human health. Therefore, the present study intends to assess the water quality for fish pond against the standards in the peri-urban area, Ibadan, Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

2.1 Literature Review

Metals with comparatively high atomic weight, atomic number, or density are referred to as heavy metals. A class of metals and metalloids with densities higher than 5g/cm³ is known as heavy metals. They are all classified as transition elements. These elements' extensive industrial, residential, agricultural, medical, and technological uses have sparked grave worries

about their possible implications on human health and the environment (Dong et al., 2023). Lead (Pb), plumbum, is a dense, bluish grey metallic element; it is among the foremost known metals (Ghazi and Millette, 1964). It is highly toxic and not biodegradable (Mandas, et al. 2020). Although used in various industrial products, it is toxic with no useful benefit for organisms (Mandas et al 2020). Lead does not break down in the environment, only changing form. The presence of lead (Pb) in drinking water can cause severe health hazards, primarily causing irreversible neurodevelopmental damage in children and cardiovascular/renal dysfunction in adults (Hsu et al. 2025). It acts as a cumulative toxicant, affecting nearly every organ in the body system, particularly the nervous and reproductive systems. No amount of lead in the body system is safe, while a higher level of lead in the blood can cause seizures and comas (WHO, 2024). Some sicknesses that are traceable to the presence of lead in the blood are high blood pressure, cardiovascular diseases, chronic kidney disease and reproductive disorders.

Figure 1: Flow of heavy metal pollution and health implication

Source: Edori & Iyama, 2020

Copper (Cu) is reddish orange in colour, it is capable of being shaped or bent and a good conductor of heat and electricity (Massaro, 2002). Cu can be discovered in the environment as a metal and in a variety of minerals (such as cuprite and malachite) and is naturally present in the Earth's crust. In some places, concentrations can range from less than 50 parts per million to several thousand parts per million. Sulfide ores provide the majority of the recovered copper. Cu is released into the environment by both man-made and natural processes. Eruptions from volcano airborne particles, forest fires, and decomposing vegetation are examples of natural occurrences. Typical human activities that release copper into the environment include copper mining, grinding, and metal manufacture. The majority of the copper present in the air, soil, and water today is a result of human activities (Zunaira et al, 2020).

Numerous sources of copper can also contaminate water, such as agricultural runoff

from farms that use insecticides containing copper. Seaweed ashes, several sea corals, human liver, and a variety of mollusks and arthropods all contain it. Human bone, nerve coverings, and connective tissue all require copper for proper growth (Yuhan et al., 2025). It has antioxidant properties. Although uncommon, copper deficiency can result in abnormalities of the neurological system, connective tissue, and bones as well as anaemia. Whole grains, dark chocolate, almonds, seeds, oysters, liver and other organ meats, and other foods are good providers of dietary copper. Potatoes, raisins, mushrooms, chickpeas, and other legumes also contain some copper. Copper intake may be increased by drinking water through copper pipes. According to certain research, inhaling copper might cause blood abnormalities, such as a drop in hemoglobin and erythrocyte counts. Muscle aches, headaches, and eye discomfort can be brought on by copper dust and fumes. Large doses of copper compounds, such as copper

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sulfate, can be fatal due to liver, renal, and nervous system failure. People who consume water from copper pipes have reported experiencing vomiting, nausea, diarrhea, and stomach pain due to high amounts of copper in the water (WHO, 2004).

An essential micronutrient for the metabolism of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates is chromium (Singha 2025). The concentration of chromium (Cr) in the Earth's crust is 100 µg/g, and its toxicity is contingent upon its chemical state (Sudeshna & Surjendu, 2023). The detrimental effects of Cr dust on workers who produce chromate have been the subject of some studies (Kozłowska et al., 2019 & Tsuchiyama et al., 2020). Additionally, Cr containing industrial wastes are significant sources of water and soil contamination, which can have detrimental effects on human health. With the exception of extraction operations where Cr deposits are located and geological settings where human activity may have altered rock compositions, anthropogenic activities have had minimal impact on the true concentration of Cr in the environment. Among many other uses, Cr is a crucial metal in the production of pigments, paint, metal plating, wood treatment, leather tanning, metallurgy, and refractory materials.

A range of plant and animal diets, as well as supplements, include zinc (Zn), an important vitamin. It may help prevent acne, inflammation, and other ailments and is essential for immune system function, cell growth, and skin health. A zinc shortage in marine biomes, particularly in Polar Regions, can jeopardize the health of primary algal populations, potentially upsetting the complex

marine trophic networks and so affecting species (Anglia, University of East). Skeletal muscle and bone store the majority of this zinc (Institute of Medicine, 2001 and King et al, 2014). However, if it is found to be deficient in the human system, it can lead to hypogonadism, which is associated with delayed wound healing, dermatitis, anorexia, developmental impairment, and reduced reproductive capability (Edori & Iyama, 2020). According to King & Cousins (2014), indications of zinc deficiency include decreased growth and development, delayed sexual maturity, skin rashes, recurrent diarrhea, poor wound healing, and behavioral issues. An estimated 2 billion people worldwide are zinc deficient due to inadequate zinc-food intake (Barbara & Emily, 2019).

Iron (Fe) is a non-toxic element that is necessary for all living organisms. An adult human's body contains around 4 grams (0.005% of body weight) of iron, primarily in the form of myoglobin and hemoglobin. These two proteins are crucial for both blood oxygen transport and muscle oxygen storage. Additionally, iron can function as a limiting nutrient for planktonic activity and is crucial to marine systems (Morel et al., 1991). Iron can reach marine systems directly from the atmosphere and through nearby rivers. After entering the ocean, iron can be recycled at the cellular level and dispersed throughout the water column via ocean mixing (Archer & Johnson, 2000). Sea ice in the Arctic contributes significantly to the distribution and storage of iron in the ocean, releasing iron back into the water when it thaws in the summer and depleting it when it freezes in the winter (Wang

et al, 2014). Deferoxamine is a particular chelating drug that can be used to bind and remove excess iron from the body as part of the complex medical management of iron toxicity (Tenenbein, 1996).

Cadmium (Cd) is a highly toxic, non-essential heavy metal that enters the human body primarily through the ingestion of contaminated food and the inhalation of tobacco smoke or industrial fumes. Because the human body has a very limited ability to excrete cadmium, it is a cumulative toxin with a biological half-life of 10 to 30 years.

There are both advantages and disadvantages to urban fish farming for urban residents. While negative effects include environmental pollution and neighbourly misunderstandings, positive effects include job creation, income, and food security. The presence of the above heavy metals in the neighbourhood water could be classified as a negative impact of fish farming. While some of them are essential to both plants and animals at low levels, their presence in food, soil, and air above the threshold poses a health risk to humans (Hogstand & Haux, 2011). Due to their toxicity, certain of these metals (Pb and Cd) are not needed by the environment or human body, even at extremely low amounts. This is due to the fact that they disrupt animals' physiological systems, resulting in various illnesses (Damek & Sawicka, 2003). Others, however, are necessary at trace amounts for healthy physiological and biochemical bodily processes, including iron, copper, zinc, and chromium (Edori & Marcus, 2017).

2.2 Concept of Water Quality

The physical, chemical, and biological properties of water that determine its fitness for particular applications, including drinking, recreation, farming, or maintaining aquatic ecosystems, are referred to as water quality (Adelowokan & Adejumo, 2025). In order to assess safety, pollution levels, and general health, such is done against defined standards; contamination is indicated by poor quality. This complex idea is characterized by a variety of physical, chemical, biological, and microbiological characteristics, guaranteeing that it satisfies the requirements for a range of applications in many industries, including residential, agricultural, and industrial (Bandh, 2025). No water is completely “pure”: scientists and this made the environmental engineers to define water quality as meeting relative thresholds for specific use.

Under the Clean Water Act (CWA), the default water quality standard for surface waters is described as “fishable and swimmable (Percival et al., 2021). This standard requires that such waters pose no risk to human health through direct contact or incidental ingestion. Many regions establish water quality standards for water bodies within their territories and designate agencies to regulate and monitor compliance with the standards. When a water body does not meet the established standards, it is classified as impaired, obligating the responsible government authority to implement a remediation plan to restore it to compliance.

Heavy metals in water bodies particularly the one used for drinking, recreation, or commercial fishing are threat. In many Nigerian cities, peri-

urban areas are largely unplanned, often characterized by informal development where residents undertake projects without permits from the appropriate authorities. Maintaining water quality in these peri-urban regions is especially challenging and costly, as much of the land is acquired through informal arrangements. Increase in the anthropogenic activities in this region directly increases the environment pollution which negatively affects the quality of both human and animal lives. Over time, the waste from these activities accumulate progressively and find their way into the water bodies which impair the quality of the water and affect aquatic organisms which are injurious to human health when consumed (Wiener, 2023).

3.0 Materials and Method

Methodology

Cross sectional and experimental survey research design was used for the study, while both primary and secondary data were sourced. A purposive sampling technique was used to select fish ponds based on relevant characteristics. Each participant adequately represented different zones of Arulogun. A total number of 62 fish ponds were identified, representing a 100% sample size for adequate inference. Water samples were then collected from the chosen fishponds in Arulogun, Ibadan and the water quality was assessed using six metals (i.e., Lead (Pb), Copper (Cu), Chromium (Cr), Zinc (Zn), Iron (Fe), and Cadmium (Cd)). The chosen water samples were then subjected to a laboratory test. Samples were collected in polypropylene bottles that

were appropriately acidified to avoid biological, chemical, and physical alterations. After being placed inside an ice box, these bottles were brought to the laboratory. Every sample was kept in a refrigerator at a temperature lower than 4 °C. Quantitative statistics (ANOVA) was used to analyse the data at $p \leq 0.05$ confidence level. The results were compared against the World Health Organisation (WHO) standard limits for fishponds and fisheries in the determination of potential contamination risks and environmental safety.

4.0 Results and Discussions

Water Quality

Water quality is a critical factor in aquaculture and fisheries, as it directly impacts the health, growth, and survival of aquatic organisms. This study analysed water samples from selected fishponds to determine the concentration of six heavy metals: Lead (Pb), Copper (Cu), Chromium (Cr), Zinc (Zn), Iron (Fe), and Cadmium (Cd), as shown in Table 1. The results were compared against the World Health Organisation (WHO) standard limits for fishponds and fisheries to assess potential contamination risks and environmental safety. This study reveals significant heavy metal contamination in fishpond water samples, raising concerns about potential industrial and agricultural pollution. The results indicate that several samples exceeded the World Health Organization (WHO) standards for key heavy metals, which could have serious implications for aquatic life and human health.

Table 1: Metal Analysis of the expected and observed mean

Location of fishpond	Pb (Ex) mg/l	Pb (Ob) mg/l	Cu (Ex) mg/l	Cu (Ob) mg/l	Cr (Ex) mg/l	Cr (O) mg/l	Zn (Ex) mg/l	Zn (Ob) mg/l	Fe (Ex) mg/l	Fe (Ob) mg/l	Cd (Ex) mg/l	Cd (Ob) mg/l
A1	0.01	1.80± 1.41	2.0	24.10 ±1.56	0.05	0.00 ±0.0 0	3.0	6.90± 0.71	0.3	34.90 ±1.27	0.00 3	0.00± 0.00
A2	0.01	0.00± 0.00	2.0	3.80± 0.85	0.05	10.0 0±0. 28	3.0	4.70± 0.71	0.3	12.10± 0.71	0.00 3	0.00± 0.00
B1	0.01	0.00± 0.00	2.0	4.20± 0.28	0.05	3.10 ±0.1 4	3.0	0.70± 0.14	0.3	13.90 ±0.42	0.00 3	0.00± 0.00
B2	0.01	0.00± 0.00	2.0	1.30± 0.14	0.05	0.00 ±0.0 0	3.0	2.00± 0.28	0.3	20.50 ±0.14	0.00 3	0.00± 0.00
C1	0.01	0.07± 0.10	2.0	1.00± 0.28	0.05	0.00 ±0.0 0	3.0	0.70± 0.14	0.3	30.00 ±0.28	0.00 3	0.20± 0.00
C2	0.01	3.10± 1.27	2.0	0.40± 0.00	0.05	0.00 ±0.0 0	3.0	1.40± 0.14	0.3	13.00 ±0.57	0.00 3	0.00± 0.00
D1	0.01	0.00± 0.00	2.0	2.40± 0.00	0.05	0.00 ±0.0 0	3.0	1.30± 0.14	0.3	12.70± 0.14	0.00 3	0.30± 0.14
D2	0.01	3.10± 2.12	2.0	2.40± 0.28	0.05	2.30 ±0.1 4	3.0	0.83± 0.01	0.3	33.50 ±0.14	0.00 3	0.10± 0.14
E	0.01	2.60± 1.70	2.0	0.90± 0.14	0.05	2.30 ±0.1 4	3.0	2.00± 0.00	0.3	3.30± 0.71	0.00 3	0.20± 0.00

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

4.3.2 Metal Analysis

Lead (Pb) levels varied between 0.00 and 3.10 mg/L, with samples A1, C1, C2, D2, and E exceeding the WHO limit of 0.01 mg/L (Table 2). The occurrence, which has a high toxicity, its presence in these samples suggests contamination from industrial or agricultural runoff, which could negatively impact fish

health and human consumers relying on these water sources. It is poisonous to humans system and can enter through several media in the environment. Acute toxicity of lead can cause gastrointestinal disorders, while continuing deposition in human anatomy can cause fatigue, infertility, menstrual disorders, depression, and sleep disturbances (Yeti et al 2020).

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Table 2: Lead (Pb) Metal Analysis Pb (mg/L)

SAMPLES	1	2	Mean	SD	MEAN±SD
A1	2.80	0.80	1.80	1.41	1.80±1.41
A2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
B1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
B2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
C1	0.00	0.14	0.07	0.10	0.07±0.10
C2	2.20	4.00	3.10	1.27	3.10± 1.27
D1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
D2	4.60	1.60	3.10	2.12	3.10±2.12
E	1.40	3.80	2.60	1.70	2.60±1.70

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2025

Copper (Cu), with respect to its concentrations, ranged from 0.40 to 24.10 mg/L, surpassing the WHO guideline of 2.00 mg/L in A1, A2, B1, and D2 (Table 3). The extremely high concentration observed (24.10 mg/L) indicates a potential source of pollution, such as copper-based pesticides. These eventually may lead to low yields for fish farmers. Also, the implication of this is that excessive levels can cause gill damage and hinder fish growth. But can copper pose a health risk to human metabolism? In the same way that some copper is necessary for health, too

much of it can be detrimental. Overconsumption of copper can lead to health problems such as nausea, gastrointestinal pain, and, in extreme cases, damage to the kidneys or liver. Coughing, sneezing, and chest pain can result from inhaling copper dust and fumes from copper-producing and processing plants. Additionally, it may negatively impact the digestive system, resulting in nausea and diarrhea. Endocrine and liver function may also be affected. (Sailer et al, 2024).

Table 3: Copper (Cu) Metal Analysis Cu (mg/L)

SAMPLE	1	2	Mean	SD	MEAN±SD
A1	25.20	23.00	24.10	1.56	24.10±1.56
A2	4.40	3.20	3.80	0.85	3.80±0.85
B1	4.40	4.00	4.20	0.28	4.20±0.28
B2	1.40	1.20	1.30	0.14	1.30±0.14
C1	0.80	1.20	1.00	0.28	1.00±0.28
C2	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.00	0.40±0.00
D1	2.40	2.40	2.40	0.00	2.40±0.00
D2	2.60	2.20	2.40	0.28	2.40±0.28
E	1.00	0.80	0.90	0.14	0.90±0.14

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2025

Regarding Chromium (Cr), the contamination was also evident, with levels ranging from 0.00 to 10.00 mg/L. According to Table 4, samples A2, B1, D2, and E exceeded the WHO limit of 0.05 mg/L, raising concerns about industrial waste disposal. Hexavalent chromium (Cr6+), in particular, poses a significant threat to aquatic organisms, causing oxidative stress and DNA damage. The substantial excess in A2 (10.00 mg/L) suggests that industrial activities may be

responsible for the contamination. Chromium (Cr) has been identified as causing various haematological problems in fish. At high concentrations, it perturbs fish behaviour and physiology, but does not generally lead to fish mortality in most cases. The effects include reductions in serum haemoglobin, erythrocyte count, and thrombocytes. Others include degeneration of proteins, fats, sterols, and glycogen (Hanser & Marrion, 2009).

Table 4: Chromium (Cr) Metal Analysis Cr (mg/L)

SAMPLE	1	2	Mean	SD	MEAN±SD
A1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
A2	10.20	9.80	10.00	0.28	10.00±0.28
B1	3.00	3.20	3.10	0.14	3.10±0.14
B2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
C1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
C2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
D1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
D2	2.40	2.20	2.30	0.14	2.30±0.14
E	2.20	2.40	2.30	0.14	2.30±0.14

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Zinc (Zn) levels ranged between 0.70 and 6.90 mg/L, exceeding the WHO standard of 3.00 mg/L in A1 and A2. The presence of excessive zinc may stem from metal plating industries or agricultural sources (Table 5). Although zinc is a vital micronutrient for aquatic species, elevated concentrations can lead to respiratory distress in fish, thereby causing a lot of loss due to a high mortality rate known as 'fish kill'. Because of its various biochemical and metabolic functions in bodily tissues and cell proliferation, it is an essential component of the human system

(Edori & Iyama, 2020). Concentrated zinc levels can cause intestinal itching, nausea, depression, illness, and cough; these symptoms are temporary (Barceloux, 1999, & Tepe, 2014). According to Ryu (2020), the overall amount of zinc in the body is roughly 1.5 g for women and 2.5 g for men. Zn concentrations above 5 mg/L are known to cause water to taste bitter and to become more opaque, particularly in residential water with an alkaline pH (Barceloux, 1999). Too much consumption of zinc can cause ataxia and lethargy.

Table 5: Zinc (Zn) Metal Analysis Zn (mg/L)

SAMPLE	1	2	Mean	SD	MEAN±SD
A1	7.40	6.40	6.90	0.71	6.90±0.71
A2	4.20	5.20	4.70	0.71	4.70±0.71
B1	0.60	0.80	0.70	0.14	0.70±0.14
B2	1.80	2.20	2.00	0.28	2.00±0.28
C1	0.60	0.80	0.70	0.14	0.70±0.14
C2	1.20	1.40	1.30	0.14	1.40±0.14
D1	1.20	1.40	1.30	0.14	1.30±0.14
D2	0.82	0.84	0.83	0.01	0.83±0.01
E	2.00	2.00	2.00	0.00	2.00±0.00

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2025

Moreover, Iron (Fe) contamination was widespread, with all samples exceeding the WHO limit of 0.30 mg/L. Observed levels ranged from 3.30 to 34.90 mg/L, with A1 showing the highest concentration (Table 6). The high levels detected suggest pollution from industrial discharge, acid mine drainage, or natural iron leaching from sediments. Excessive iron can clog fish gills, leading to respiratory distress and potential mortality. In particular, large amounts of free iron in the blood might result from an overdose of iron injected into the human body. At this point, free iron causes toxicity. Iron levels in humans become toxic

when they exceed 20 mg per kilogram of body mass; a dose of 60 mg per kilogram is considered lethal. To maintain the necessary levels, human iron metabolism requires a minimum amount of iron in the diet. Extremely reactive free radicals that can damage lipids, proteins, DNA, and other components of cells are produced when high blood levels of free ferrous iron interact with peroxides. Iron's detrimental effects on cells in the heart, liver, and other organs can lead to liver failure and long-term organ damage (Bloomer, & Brown, 2019).

Table 6: Iron (Fe) Metal Analysis Fe (mg/L)

SAMPLE	1	2	Mean	SD	MEAN±SD
A1	34.00	35.80	34.90	1.27	34.90±1.27
A2	12.60	11.60	12.10	0.71	12.10±0.71
B1	14.20	13.60	13.90	0.42	13.90±0.42
B2	20.40	20.60	20.50	0.14	20.50±0.14
C1	30.20	29.80	30.00	0.28	30.00±0.28
C2	12.60	13.40	13.00	0.57	13.00±0.57
D1	12.60	12.80	12.70	0.14	12.70±0.14
D2	33.60	33.40	33.50	0.14	33.50±0.14
E	3.80	2.80	3.30	0.71	3.30±0.71

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Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Furthermore, Cadmium (Cd), one of the most toxic heavy metals to aquatic life, was detected at concentrations up to 0.30 mg/L. According to Table 7, the samples C1, D1, D2, and E exceeded the WHO standard of 0.003 mg/L. Possible sources include pollution from batteries, electroplating industries, and agricultural runoff. Even at low concentrations, cadmium poses significant risks, including kidney damage and bioaccumulation in fish tissues. When Cd is found in human, animal, or plant tissue, it tends to infect important amino acids and build up at very high quantities in the proximal tubular

cells. This can further change the structure and properties of the kidney and lung, as well as cause brittleness in the bones (Edori & Iyama). High levels of Cd can cause the liver to malfunction, newborns to lose weight, and pregnant women to give birth prematurely (Sensoy, 2023). In the study of Hanser & Marrion (2009), procreative disorders, cardiac and vascular neurology, haematological, kidney dysfunction, hepatocyte damage, and other critical bodily organs are additional diseases linked to cadmium consumption.

Table 7: Iron (Fe) Metal Analysis Cd (mg/L)

SAMPLE	1	2	Mean	SD	MEAN±SD
A1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
A2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
B1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
B2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
C1	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.00	0.20±0.00
C2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
D1	0.40	0.20	0.30	0.14	0.30±0.14
D2	0.20	0.00	0.10	0.14	0.10±0.14
E	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.00	0.20±0.00

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

From this study, it is evident that heavy metal contamination in the fishpond water is a pressing concern, with iron, lead, copper, and chromium posing the most severe risks. Furthermore, we can consider that widespread iron pollution suggests either industrial discharge or natural sediment leaching, while lead and cadmium contamination point to sources such as industrial waste and agricultural runoff. The water samples show widespread heavy metal enrichment. According to Figure 2,

Iron (Fe) is consistently elevated across all ponds, while Location A1 appears to be the most heavily impacted by multiple metals (Pb, Cu, Zn, and Fe). These levels suggest the water may be unsuitable for fish farming without remediation. The presence of high copper and chromium levels in certain samples calls for urgent remediation efforts to mitigate risks to aquatic ecosystems and human consumers. Immediate intervention is required to address the

contamination sources and prevent long-term environmental damage.

Fig 2: Proportions of heavy metal in each sample.

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

4.3.4 Statistical Analysis of Water Samples

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Table 8 showed the main and interaction effects of both the type of metal and the water samples significantly impact the concentration levels. It can further be explained using the corrected model of a Significance (Sig.) value of .001. Since this is less than the standard threshold of 0.05, then the model is statistically significant. This means that, taken together, the type of metal and the specific water sample significantly explain the variations in concentration. For metal is the most influential factor with a Sig. value of .001 and the highest F-statistic (29.995), there are significant differences

between the concentrations of the five different metals tested. The Eta Squared ($\eta^2=.658$),) indicates that approximately 65.8% of the variance in concentration is strictly due to the type of metal. The effect of metal on concentration is highly significant ($F_{(5,78)} = 29.995, p<.05, \eta^2=.658$), indicating that different metals contributed substantially to variations in concentration. Similarly, the effect of the sample (water sources) is also significant ($F_{(4,78)} = 4.292, p<.05, \eta^2 = .180$), though it has a lower effect size compared to metal. This implies that while both factors play a role in influencing concentration levels, the type of metal has a stronger impact than the water sample itself.

Table 8: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing the main and interaction effects of metal and water samples on concentration

Source	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta. Sq
Corrected Model	5972.092	29	205.934	8.594	.001	.762
Intercept	2105.280	1	2105.280	87.858	.001	.530
Metal	3593.719	5	718.744	29.995	.001	.658
Water sample	411.426	4	102.857	4.292	.003	.180
<u>2-way interaction</u>						
Metal*Sample	869.416	20	43.471	1.814	.033	.317
Error	1869.052	78	23.962			
Corrected Total	7841.144	107				

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2025

Ho: There is no significant main and interaction effects of metal and water samples (A1-E) on concentration

R Squared= .762 (Adjusted R Squared = .673)

Furthermore, the interaction effect between metal and water sample (Metal*Sample) is statistically significant ($F_{(20,78)} = 1.814, p < .05, \eta^2 = .317$), revealing that the effect of metal on concentration varies depending on the water sample used. Although the interaction effect has a smaller effect size compared to metal alone, it still contributed meaningfully to the overall model.

The analysis confirms that the concentration levels are not uniform. The type of metal is the primary driver of concentration differences, but the specific location of the water sample also plays a significant role. Most importantly, the significant interaction suggests you cannot generalise the metal levels across all water samples; they behave differently depending on the combination.

Conclusion

This study investigated the environmental quality of peri-urban neighbourhoods in Ibadan, Nigeria, with a focus on the impact of fish farming activities on environmental resources. The findings highlight a critical environmental challenge: significant heavy-metal contamination within local fishponds. Laboratory analysis revealed that concentrations of some heavy metals frequently exceeded the safety limits stipulated by the World Health Organisation (WHO), making them toxic to human health. While the fish farming sector provides essential socioeconomic benefits, including job creation, poverty alleviation, and food security, these advantages are currently threatened by deteriorating environmental quality. The high reliance of local operators on natural streams (54%) further underscores the vulnerability of the local ecosystem to unregulated anthropogenic activities. In summary, the presence of heavy metals above threshold levels represents a pressing risk to both aquatic life and human

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health. Without immediate intervention to remediate existing contamination and regulate land-use activities in these dynamic peri-urban zones, the sustainability of the aquaculture industry and the well-being of the surrounding community remain at significant risk.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that urgent and adequate attention be given to the management of peri-

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urban regions to mitigate the significant environmental and health risks identified. Given the evidence of widespread heavy metal contamination, particularly the excessive levels of Iron (Fe), Lead (Pb), and Cadmium (Cd) that frequently exceed World Health Organisation (WHO) safety thresholds, it is essential to implement regulated controls on human activities in these areas.

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